

WHAT IS A CONTENT IN TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE?

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Annotation: One of the important research issues discussed is the content component of teaching foreign languages. The content components are of direct relevance to the aim of training foreign languages. Aim determines the content that is if it is convinced that the content is gained during the lessons as well the result of these lessons take to the aim. Practical objectives of teaching English include clarifying how to use specific language material and gaining experience, but there are certain precise limits in terms of solving methodological problems.

Key words: methodology, how, what, books, topics, elementary, content, elementary, school, college, lyceum

Teaching a language involves teaching its system, the rules of use and ways of usage, as well as the ability to use that system to understand and produce messages. By the rules of use and usage, we mean the grammatical, lexical, and pragmatic aspects of the system (that is, the grammar, vocabulary, and functions of that language) In addition to that, every language teacher wants to create a solid lesson plan for students and this plan should provide with all the most crucial elements of language. First on the focus is to find out materials and analyze them based on the age group of the learners of English. Since, there are a great distinction amongst educational places, such as, pupils in school are taught beginner or elementary levels of English. In this way, I want to choose one education centre which is called “BEST school” and then I will tell you some of the contents, methods in teaching different age groups and levels. Why did I choose the especially education center not school or college. Because you can meet school, college and lyceum students in one place, besides we can have clear idea of their level which means that teachers will be able to create a solid and appropriate lesson plan, with a term “syllabus”.

Foremost we have to address this questions;

- WHAT TO TEACH ?
- WHOM TO TEACH ?

Here I will share my own lesson plan to introduce you to the content of English being taught for elementary level students:

DAY	CLASSWORK	HOMEWORK
INTRODUCTION LESSON	1. Introducing to the rules and course materials 10 minutes 2. Warm up activity: 5 minutes 3. Introduction unit: Personal information (solutions) 20 minutes 2. Talking about ability and asking permission (solutions) 20 minutes 3. Listening tactics (Introductions and names) 30 minutes 4. Speaking by using cards 30 minutes 5. Giving Homework 5 minutes	1. Books 2. Speaking: describe yourself and talk about your ability 3. Revise vocabulary 4. Making sentences 5. Not being late, punishment, asking permission
LESSON 1	1. Playing Kahoot.it test (to ask vocabularies) and exchanging copybooks 10 minutes 2. Solutions Unit 1 (first half) explaining 10 minutes and exercises 15 minutes 3. Listening tactics (Describing people) 20 minutes 4. Grammarway unit 1 explaining 15 minutes and exercises 10 minutes 5. Explain speaking Part	1. Solutions Unit 1 vocabularies 2. Grammarway unit 1 exercises (all) 3. Writing: Famous families 4. Speaking: Part 1 questions (general interview) 5. Video from Solutions 6. Listening tactics all task 2 exercises

	<p>1 (dos and don't) 15 minutes</p> <p>6. Song listening and gap filling 5 minutes</p> <p>7. British council reading 15 minutes</p> <p>8. Giving homework 5 minutes</p>	
LESSON 2	<p>1. Playing online wordwall quiz (to ask vocabularies) and exchanging copybooks 10 minutes</p> <p>2. Solutions Unit 1 (second half) explaining 10 minutes and exercises 15 minutes</p> <p>3. Listening (Clothes) 20 minutes</p> <p>4. Grammarway unit 2 explaining 15 minutes and exercises 10 minutes</p> <p>5. Explain speaking (expressing feelings) 15 minutes</p> <p>6. "Who am I" game 5 minutes</p> <p>7. British council listening 15 minutes</p> <p>8. Giving homework 5 minutes</p>	<p>1. Essential Unit 1 and 2</p> <p>2. Grammarway unit 2 (all)</p> <p>3. Writing: A personal profile</p> <p>4. Essential 1 and 2 reading</p> <p>5. Video from Solutions</p> <p>6. Listening tactics all task 2 exercises</p>

Here you can see just the beginning of the plan and based on this I also showed contents, namely, what are the grammar, vocabulary, what are the topics and time spend. Elementary lesson contents for English language students generally focus on areas such as family, home life, routines, interests, food, sport,

travel, the body and appearance. These topics are fairly easy to talk about with rudimentary language skills. Grammar topics include present tenses, the present perfect continuous, the past perfect, zero conditionals, reported speech, relative clauses, passive voice, intensifiers and much, much more. Furthermore, there are methods used to teach these contents in classroom. For example, teachers apply more gamified methods for school pupils. We are living in the golden age of technology and it enables teachers to use various websites or platforms to create activities. Above, I brought out kahoot.it to test student's knowledge and it is basically for elementary level students (another comes with the name wordwall.com).

Moving on pre-intermediate lesson contents for English language students generally focus on areas such as culture, the environment, careers, and health. And of course, debate and discussion lessons become more useful as students become more fluent. Students are better able to discuss social trends in areas such as technology and business related fields of advertising and tourism. These topics also have the benefits of being quite interesting, engaging and relevant. When it comes to grammar, this is for pre-intermediate builds knowledge of form and structure to enable the connection of ideas. They are; advanced adverbs, advanced prepositions, as.....as, activities, connecting words, complex, defining and non-defining relative clauses future continuous.

Next steps are taken by a number of factors, I mean, If we want to teach more upper level of English (upper-intermediate, advanced) we should approach with diversity and should not repeat before-taught topics. This may cause dull atmosphere in the classroom. Some factors that you will want to consider in selecting your topic are:

- goals of the curriculum
- what the learners already know
- needs and characteristics of the learners
- school district, state, national, and subject matter standards
- educational research on best practices
- everyday matters such as availability of equipment and supplies, the season of the year, or alterations in the school schedule

Considering that their English is quite good already (namely advanced level students) we can do a needs analysis. A needs analysis is important no matter what level you are teaching but particularly for advanced students. Advanced students are able to identify what they need in terms of their language development and are able to articulate this. This will be a big help when

planning your lessons. Do not focus on grammar! When you think about it, your advanced students have probably been sitting in a language classroom for several years, each year going over the same grammatical points. By the time they get to advanced, we cannot blame them for being bored of grammar. Besides, knowing the rules of grammar does not necessarily mean they are able to utilise them correctly, when in fact it's opportunities for practice that they need. Introducing natural language is another approach. Bringing more obscure language into the classroom is so authentic way. At this level you can go beyond basic vocabulary and focus more on authentic language – colloquialisms, collocations and idiomatic language. Plus, you can use authentic materials to show your students how the language is used in real life.

Lastly, we will talk about

- **HOW TO TEACH ?**

There are very famous and productive methods of teaching English. Some popular methods are Grammar-Translation, Direct Method, Audio-Lingual, Suggestopedia, and Silent Way, Task-Based learning. The methodology of teaching English differs from person to person. A teacher in a classroom with 25-50 students, the sole speaker striking facts and theories at the students, is the traditional teaching method. Like any other topic, teaching language has undergone a lot of changes. It has shifted to role-plays, interactive games, short visuals, etc. from the traditional ways. These are universal methods and based on the age, level and the educational places (school, college, lyceum) it can have a small differences in terms of their difficulty.

In conclusion, One of the main assumptions of English teaching is to give such materials, which should enable learners to acquire such language skills they will need in typical situations they meet in their professional life. So content of teaching deals with “what to teach?” and “how to teach?” questions

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